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XALQARO JURNAL

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AFRIKADAGI QOLOQLIK MUAMMOSINING TAVSIFI

Annotatsiya. Shubhasiz, Afrika inson va tabiiy resurslarga boy, ammo u rivojlanmagan, qashshoq va qoloq mintaqa bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu paradoksni keltirib chiqaruvchi ko'plab omillar mavjud. Ushbu maqolada Afrikadagi rivojlanmaslikning mohiyati, asosiy sabablari va oqibatlarini muhokama qiladi. Afrikadagi rivojlanmaslik inqirozi va uning natijalari Afrikaning rivojlanish intilishlariga jiddiy ta'sir qiladi. Shu bilan birga, muammoni hal qilishga yordam beradigan ba'zi yechimlar taklif etishga harakat qilingan. Maqolada ta'kidlanishicha, agar taklif etilgan yechimlar qat'iy amalga oshirilsa, Afrika rivojlanib, rivojlangan davlatlar qatoriga qo'shilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: sharh, muammo, rivojlanmaslik, Afrika.

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ОБЗОР ПРОБЛЕМЫ НЕДОРАЗВИТИЯ В АФРИКЕ

Аннотация. Без сомнения, Африка богата человеческими и природными ресурсами, однако она остается недоразвитой, бедной и отсталой. Существует множество факторов, обуславливающих этот парадокс. В данном контексте в статье анализируются коренные причины и последствия недоразвития Африки. Этот кризис недоразвития и его последствия существенно влияют на стремление Африки к развитию. Также предпринимаются усилия по предложению некоторых решений, которые помогут в значительной мере решить эту проблему. В заключение статьи утверждается, что, если строго придерживаться предложенных решений, Африка сможет развиваться и присоединиться к числу передовых стран.

Ключевые слова: Африка, обзор, проблема, недоразвитие.

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AN OVERVIEW OF THE PROBLEM OF UNDER-DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA

Abstract. Africa without doubt is blessed with abundant human and natural resources, yet, she is underdeveloped, poor and backward. There are a lot of factors responsible for this paradox. It is against this background that the paper discusses meaning, nature, features, the root causes and effects of underdevelopment of Africa. This crisis of underdevelopment in Africa and its attendant consequences really affect Africa's quest for development. This paper addresses this problem of underdevelopment because it is presumed that Africa cannot make any headway without tackling or proffering solutions to this problem. Efforts are equally made to proffer some proposed solutions which will go a long way to solve this problem. The paper therefore concludes that if all the suggested solutions are strictly adhered to, Africa will develop and join the league of advanced Nations.

Keywords: Overview, problem, underdevelopment, Africa.

Introduction

The primary purpose of this paper is to provide an insight into the problem of underdevelopment in Africa. It is disheartening and disturbing to note that years after independence, Africa has not developed, despite the fact that she is endowed with abundant human and natural resources. George affirms this when he asked: "Is it not a paradox, that Nigeria that compared favourably in the growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) with these proximate economies will have poor income per capita, extreme poverty and inequalities, a high unemployment and inflation rates and other poor socio-economic indicators?" [George Oladapo, 2012, p.67.] Timamy avers that:

One of Africa's most disconcerting paradoxes is that, despite being a treasure trove of abundant economic and mineral resources (many of which are strategic), the continent continues to wallow in paralyzing poverty among other immiserizing conditions: crushing debt and growing indebtedness, civil strife and violent conflicts, vampiristic leaderships and impoverishing misgovernance, predatory corruption and deepening economic malaise, intensifying environmental degradation and acute health emergencies, to name but a few. Over the last four or so decades, Africa has served as a dumping ground of one "development" model after another, virtually, all external blueprints proving fruitless and horrendously unsuccessful" [Timamy Khalil, 2007, p.78].

The problem of underdevelopment in Africa concerns everybody and as the saying goes in Nigeria, "there is no tribalism in the mortuary", "hunger does not recognize tribal marks", hence, it behoves on all of us to get involved in the problem

of underdevelopment in Africa. Africa, by all known standard is not supposed to be poor. Therefore, all factors associated with the problem of underdevelopment of Africa must be removed and tackled so that Africa can develop.

Meaning of Underdevelopment

The word “underdevelopment” has different meanings. It may mean the blockage which forestalls a rational transformation of social structure. Lewis, identifies some of these meanings. According to Lewis, “a country may be underdeveloped in the sense that its technology is backward, when compared with that of other countries, or in the sense that its institutions are relatively unfavourable to investment, or in the sense that capital resources per head are low when compared, say with Western Europe, or in the same sense that output per head is low, or in the sense that it has valuable natural resources (minerals, water, soil) which it has not yet begin to use” [Lewis W. A., 1963. p 33].

However, “underdeveloped” has other meanings which Lewis does not seem to recognize. For instance, a country can also be underdeveloped in the sense in which most of its citizens live at, a little over, or slightly below the subsistence level. In other words, a country is also underdeveloped if the quality of life of the majority of its people is low. A team of United Nations’ experts defines economically backward country as one in which “per capita income is low when compared with per capita real incomes of the U.S.A., Canada, Australia and Western Europe” [Awolowo Obafemi, 1972, p. 45]. Per capita income is used as a parameter of measuring the development of societies. It is obtained by dividing the National Income by the number of inhabitants to get an idea of the average wealth of each inhabitant. On one hand, countries such as Britain, Japan etc having high per capita incomes are regarded as developed countries. On the other hand, countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Togo, etc. which have low per capita incomes are said to be underdeveloped. Again, Awolowo defines underdeveloped country as “one whose natural resources are partly utilized, partly underutilized, and partly mis-utilized, and in which there is a gross deficiency in the quality of the three productive agents of labour, capital and organization” [Awolowo Obafemi].

In Rodney’s opinion, underdevelopment is not absence of development, because every people have developed in one way or another and to a greater or lesser extent [Rodney Walter, 1972 p.67.]. He is of the belief that underdevelopment makes sense only as a means of comparing levels of development. It is very much tied to the fact human social development has been uneven and from a strictly economic view point, some human groups have advanced further by producing more and becoming wealthier. The moment that one group appears to be wealthier than others, some enquiry is bound to take place as to the reason for the difference. After Britain had begun to move ahead of the rest of Europe in the eighteen century, the famous British economist, Adam Smith felt it necessary to look into the causes behind the ‘wealth of nations’. At the same time, many Russians were very concerned about the fact that the country was ‘backward’ in comparison with England, France and Germany in the 18th century and subsequently, in the 19th century. Rodney maintains

that our main pre-occupation is with the differences in wealth between on the one hand, Europe and North America and on the other hand, Africa, Asia and Latin America [Rodney Walter, 1972. p.55]. In comparison with the first, the second group can be said to be backward or underdeveloped. At all times, therefore, one of the ideas behind underdevelopment is a comparative one. What this means is that it is possible to compare the economic conditions at two different periods for the same country and determine whether or not it has been developed; and (more importantly) it is possible to compare the economies of any two countries or sets of countries at any given period in time.

Another meaning of underdevelopment according to him is that it expresses a particular relationship of exploitation: namely, the exploitation of one country by another. He therefore posits that “all of the countries named as ‘underdeveloped’ with which the World is now pre-occupied is a product of capitalist, imperialist and colonialist exploitation” [Rodney Walter, 1972, p.45]. He declares in categorical term that African and Asian societies were developing independently until they were taken over directly or indirectly by the capitalist powers. When that happens, exploitation increases and the export of surplus ensues, depriving the societies of the benefit of their natural resources and labour. This without doubt, is an integral part of underdevelopment in the contemporary sense.

Nature of Underdevelopment

Underdevelopment has various natures such as economic, social, and political underdevelopment. The most noticeable aspect of poverty in the majority of Third World countries is economic underdevelopment. This is manifested at the national level by some combination of low per-capita income [technically expressed as low Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capital], highly unequal income distribution, poor infrastructure (including communications and transportation), limited use of modern technology and low consumption of energy. At the individual level, economic underdevelopment connotes widespread poverty, including unemployment, substandard housing, poor health conditions and inadequate nutrition [Handelman Howard, 2005, p. 3]. Poverty and poor public policy have often adversely affected social conditions in the Third World, narrowing opportunities for human development. Consequently, among the greatest challenges facing less developed countries has been improving their educational systems. Indeed, expanding education, particularly raising literacy rates, is a major prerequisite for economic and political modernization. Political underdevelopment involves the non-creation of specialized and differentiated government institutions that effectively carry out necessary functions, such as collecting tax revenues, defending national borders, maintaining political stability, stimulating economic development, improving the quality of human life and communicating with the citizenry.

Features of Underdevelopment

Africa is number one on the list of the underdeveloped areas of the World. But whenever we think of the development of Africa, our minds turn at building of factories and hotels, the construction of roads, the establishment of mercantile marines and airlines and so on and so forth. All of these, which are eminently desirable things in themselves, are development symbols, but not the real development itself. Many eminent economists, including Leibenstein, Rostov, Mount Joy, Meir and Baldwin, and Lewis to mention a few, have devoted a good deal of time to the study of the economics of underdevelopment. From their writings, we can gather all the characteristics of an under-developed economy, which includes ignorance, illiteracy, disease, calorie deficiency, dependence on subsistence agriculture and excessive underemployment of the rural population, deficiency in techniques, organization and capital [Awolowo Obafemi, 1977, p. 66]. Elsewhere, Awolowo goes further by saying that:

the characteristic features of an underdeveloped country are poverty, ignorance, illiteracy and poor health, superstition, dependence on subsistence agriculture, excessive and widespread underemployment, unwholesome foreign dominated economy epitomized in unfavourable terms of trade, unstable export markets, a persistent adverse balance of payments caused by dwindling foreign reserves, deficiency in technological, capital and technical and manpower know-how and widening social gap and stratification between the rich and the poor in the society” [Ogunmodede Francis, 1985, p. 215].

Again, Rodney’s views on the features of underdevelopment are very germane here. In a nutshell, these features are: lack of heavy industry, inadequate production of food, unscientific agriculture [Rodney Walter, 1972, p. 26]. Also, it has been noted with irony that the principal ‘industry’ of many underdeveloped countries is administration. He states that the salaries given to the elected politicians is higher than that given to a British member of parliaments and the number of parliamentarians in the underdeveloped African countries is also relatively high [Rodney Walter, 1972, p. 27]. For instance, in Nigeria, we have three hundred and sixty (360) members in the House of Representatives; while in the Senate, we have one hundred and nine (109) members, totaling four hundred sixty-nine (469). It is essential to point out that in describing a typical underdeveloped economy, the high disproportion of the locally distributed wealth goes into the pockets of a privileged few. For instance, Ezekwesili (former Minister of Education) says “Since 2005, the National Assembly members alone have been allocated one trillion naira (₦1tr), “she said while also lamenting that “82 per cent of Nigeria’s budgetary cost gets for recurrent expenditure.” [Obiageli Ezekwesili, 2013, p. 2]

To buttress her claim that much was being spent servicing those in government, she said Nigerian legislators are the highest paid in the world”. He also believes that “any diagnosis of underdevelopment in Africa will reveal not just low per capita income, but, also protein deficiencies [Obiageli Ezekwesili, 2013, P. 36]. Again, African economies are integrated into the very structure of the developed capitalist economies, and they are integrated in a manner that is unfavourable to

Africa and ensures that Africa is dependent on the big capitalist countries. Indeed, structural dependence is one of the characteristics of underdevelopment [Obiageli Ezekwesili, 2013, p. 34].

Causes of Underdevelopment

Having seen the features of underdevelopment above, it will be very easy for us to know and possibly delve into the causes of underdevelopment. It will be worthwhile to ask some questions that are pivotal and germane on the causes of underdevelopment before highlighting these causes. Given this therefore: How do we account for these causes? What are the factors responsible for these causes? Are these causes internally motivated or not? Are they as a result of misguided economic planning? Achebe asks “How does Nigeria, bring all the human and material resources it has to bear on its development? How do we clean up the Niger Delta? What do we need to do to bring an end to organised ethnic bigotry? How can we place the necessary checks and balances in place that will reduce the decadence, corruption, and sustained development?” [Achebe Chinua, 2012, p. 252].

According to Opafola, causes of underdevelopment of countries such as Nigeria are divided into two; namely, external and internal causes. External causes include slavery, colonialism, neo-colonialism and “Worldwide recession” [Opafola Sulaimon, 1997, P. 7]. We agree with Rodney that the European slave trade was a basic factor in African underdevelopment. Also, the new method of exploitation is known as neo-colonialism. It is the method employed by the economically advanced countries to control or influence the economies of their former colonies or underdeveloped countries. In most cases, the imperialists use multinational corporations to achieve their objectives. In Ogundowole’s opinion “the root cause of the bulk of developmental problems of the new states lies in foreign relations. Most of the new states allow wide open unrestricted trade and economic interaction between them and the advanced capitalist states” [Ogundowole Kolawole, 1988, 238]. It is ironical that rather than working for their own self-reliance, most of the new states – that is, economically backward states not only subordinate themselves to the imperialist countries and their agents, but, also, facilitate the development of the latter clique. The truth of the matter is that economically backward countries maintain links with the following international institutions which are further used by the economically advanced countries to perpetuate their underdevelopment: International Monetary Fund (IMF), International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (I.B.R.D.), World bank etc.

Some of the internal causes of underdevelopment are: duplications in activities, institutions; functions and enterprises. Employment of foreigners to handle jobs that can be done by indigenes or natives; award of contracts to foreign firms to the disadvantage of local firms. Others are: mismanagement of human, natural and financial resources; natural causes such as drought; dependence on one or two export products as foreign exchange earners also contribute to the underdevelopment of economically backward countries. We equally have other

factors such as: low capita income, low level of technology, heavy dependence on foreign aids, grants and loans, political instability and high rate of inflation, etc.

The Roots of Underdevelopment of Africa: Economic, Technological, Socio-Cultural and Political Factors.

Africa, without doubt, is well endowed with mineral and primary energy resources. African potential is shown to be greater everyday with new discoveries of mineral wealth. In a way, underdevelopment is a paradox; this is because, Africa is rich in both human and natural resources. Ogungbemi says that this paradox of Africa has both human and natural resources at its disposal, and on the other hand, Africa is the poorest and least developed continent in the World. Kwame Nkrumah and Ali Mazrui give us a general geographical view and enormous natural wealth with which Africa is endowed with respectively [Ogungbemi Segun, 2007, P.

3]. According to Nkrumah “Africa and its islands, with a land area of some twelve million square miles could easily contain within it and with room to spare the whole of India, Europe, Japan, the British Isles, Scandinavian and New Zealand. The United States of America could easily be fitted into the Sahara Desert. Africa is geographically compact and in terms of natural resources potentially the richest continent in the World.” [Nkrumah Kwame, 1970, p.13]

Writing on the enormous natural wealth with which Africa is endowed, Ali Mazrui states that “estimates of Africa’s resources are on the whole tentative. Not enough prospect in for resources under the ground has taken place, but it is fair to say that Africa has 96 percent of the non-communist World’s diamonds, 60 percent of its gold, 42 percent of its cobalt, 34 percent of its bauxite and 28 percent of its uranium. Africa’s iron reserves are probably twice those of the United States, and its reserves of chrome are the most important by far outside the Soviet Union” [Mazrui Ali, 1980, p.71].

Economic Factor

Walter Rodney states that the question as to who and what is responsible for African underdevelopment can be answered at two levels. Firstly, the answer is that the operation of the imperialist system bears major responsibility for African economic retardation by draining African wealth and by making it impossible to develop more rapidly the resources of the continent. Secondly, one has to deal with those who manipulate the system and those who are either agents or unwitting accomplices of the said system. The capitalists of Western Europe were the ones who actively extended their exploitation from inside Europe to cover the whole of Africa [Rodney Walter].

Technological Factor

Technology is the practice of any or all of the applied sciences that have practical value and or industrial use. Science and technology are the bedrock of national development and indeed the primary basis for the socio-economic advancement of any nation. The new industrial giants of South-East-Asia: Taiwan,

Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Thailand and Korea are good examples of the transformational effect of science and technology. Many countries are increasing their already massive investments in science and technology viz., the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan and the United States. The relevance of Science and technology to any nation cannot be over-emphasized. For instance, science can abolish poverty and excessive hours of labour [Russell Bertrand, 1985, p.97]. Again, “with the new forms of transportation, one can in a few hours travel to distant cities that once took months to reach. With electronic technologies (radio, television, computer networks and so on), the speed, range and scope of communication have vastly increased. The combination of visual image and auditory message has an immediacy not found in the linear sequence of the printed World. These new media offer the possibility of instant Worldwide communication, greater interaction, understanding and mutual appreciation in the “global village”. Also, among the general claims of the contribution of technology to man’s life is that of mass production of material goods and services to man. Through technology, man could produce sufficient, even excess food and other material goods with less effort. In the industrialized nations of today for instance, agricultural technology has made it possible for man to produce more than his immediate food needs. The same advancement has been witnessed also in manufacturing and industries, etc. Also, in managerial services, technology has promoted improved skills resulting in higher and improved services [Nwoko Matthew, 1992, p.112]. These and many more are some of the benefits of science and technology to any Nation, hence, it can be said with all honesty and candour that science and technology are the bedrock of national development and indeed the primary basis for the socio-economic advancement of any nation. But, despite these benefits, Nigeria, for instance, has not yet been able to break through in science and technology. Ndubuisi captures this when he opines that “as a developing nation, Nigeria requires the requisite skills, technical know-how, machines and raw materials for accelerated development [Ndubuisi F. N., 2001, p. 117]. Thus, in the national policy on education, emphasis is placed on the study of science and technology that could enhance the acquisition of skills needed for the operation of our industrial concerns. It is equally on record that “Africa still depends on Asian-oriented scientific and technological pattern and products for survival. She is conspicuously absent on the World’s science and technology stage” Science and technology are almost absent in Nigeria and Africa and as a result, have contributed in no small measure to her underdevelopment.

Socio-cultural Factor

This is one of the roots of Africa’s underdevelopment. But here, it is to be noted that the term culture will be explained and one basic social factor which is corruption. What then is culture? Culture according to Babawale encompasses the tangible and intangible as it also incorporates the subtotal of the material and immaterial tools, art work of art of a people and knowledge accumulated by the people” [Babawale Tunde, 2004, p.9]. The peculiarity of a given culture is a function of its distinctiveness as it relates to its impact on the attitudes, aspirations,

motivations, representations, skills, and behaviour of the people celebrating some and discarding others. Without mincing words, we need a kind of cultural renaissance to enable us face challenges. By this, I mean the patronage of culture, which should concern itself with the entire way of life of the Nigerian people; their creative, artistic, scientific and technological capabilities. If we may add: are there lessons from other lands? The response is affirmative. “Development in East Asia remains one of the global economy’s most significant post-war developments. Taking over from Japan, from the 1990s and beyond, China and the ‘Little Tigers’ of Singapore, Taiwan, and most recently the South-East Asian economies, including Indonesia and Malaysia, have filled the top ranks of the World’s economies in terms of not only their overall growth rates, but also of their human capital development, industrial and export growth rates” Literature on Chinese success story reveals that the rudiments of an industrial base were built on culture and traditional practices that are still being exploited even now that country has opened up to capitalist influences. It is worthy to note that China’s current economic success story would not have happened so soon, but, for this meaningful synergy between traditional values and modernity. Today, regardless of her population, size and diversity, an appreciable percentage of Chinese population is still largely agrarian living on basic Chinese culture and even pursuing aggressive export of part thereof. From drugs to wears, foodstuffs and consumables, every Chinese is a proud culture ambassador for China.

Again, it is to be stressed that Chinese sense of moderation is indeed exemplary. Proud as they are of their culture, style, taste and values, they have been making substantial gains from their creativity, exploring their environment and producing and packaging just anything from bamboo through plants, herbs, fish and fish products, to mention but a few. Again, Malaysia has garnered substantial goodwill from her culture potential so much so that her hospitality industry smells and tastes Malay traditional values Singapore is yet another good success story. Small as it is, the country had a diverse population of 2.5 million of people comprising 70 percent Chinese, 20 percent Malay and 10 percent Indian and virtually no resources, but responds meaningfully to the dynamics of globalization, information and telecommunication technology. With political economy deeply rooted in Singaporean tradition, productivity of her nationals reflects greatly in her annual earnings as distinct from and far beyond what is prevalent in countries like Nigeria and many other reservoirs of global energy resources. From this, it can be deduced that failure to embrace our culture is one of the causes of our underdevelopment.

On the social level, corruption is identified as one of the enemies of progress and development. As we all know, corruption is a cankerworm that has eaten into the fabric of our society at every level. Oladipo corroborates this when he says that “accountability and transparency are crucial to development. These qualities, unfortunately, have been in short supply in Nigeria. Small wonder, then that there has been a consistent mismatch between opportunities and accomplishments in the economic history of Nigeria. The consequences of this mismatch can be seen in the problems of inflation, unemployment, poverty and human degradation which now

define social existence in the country” [Oladipo and Olorunyomi, 1999, p.61]. According to Unah, corruption is essentially the product of man’s greed for earthly grandeur, power and authority [Unah Jim, 1995, p.124]. Also, contributing to this is Chinua Achebe who maintains that “corruption goes with power; therefore, to hold any useful discussion of corruption, we must first locate it where it properly belongs – in the ranks of the powerful” [Achebe Chinua, 1983, p.38].

At this juncture, we shall now outline some meanings or definitions of corruption; its nature, forms, causes and effects. Hence, corruption can be defined as “the perversion of integrity or state of affairs through bribery, favour or moral depravity. Corruption takes place when at least two parties have interacted to change the structure or processes of society or the behaviour of functions in order to produce dishonest, unfaithful or defiled situations” [Azenabor Godwin, 2007, p. 2]. So corruption often goes with obligations and self-centered interest; corruption is asking, giving or taking a fee; the perversion or obstruction of the performance of such a task. It involves the violation of some existing order or norms. It has also been perceived as an act which deviates from the formal rule of conduct governing the actions of someone in a position by public authority, because of private regarding motive such as wealth, power or status. We can equally posit that it is all about dishonesty, about influencing situations or people, with or without monetary inducement to gain an undeserved favour.

According to Momoh, corruption is the acceptance or the giving of something in the form of cash or kind like presents, gifts or bodily pleasures in order to perform an act, which one is in the position to perform or can cause to be performed. In other words, a corrupt practice is one in which the performance of an act has been induced” [Momoh C. S., 1991, p.115]. With these definitions, we shall now proceed to examine the nature and forms of corruption. Corruption in Nigeria has been so pervasive and ubiquitous, that it manifests in different ways and perspectives. The nature of corruption can be a solo undertaking, clandestine and sometimes even open. Its nature is such that it is located in the social, political and economic arrangements which govern the organization of society. It can also be contextual. It also differs conceptually from one culture to the other. We must also note that corruption in Nigeria takes many forms; such as using official stationery, using government drugs, dressings and hospital equipment for private purposes, using government labour for private work, misuse of government motor vehicles for private purposes, demanding sex from female applicants for jobs demanding money from applicants for jobs and contracts, tampering with applications, contract documents and payment vouchers, misuse of overseas tours, election malpractices among others [Adebayo Augustus, 1986, p.20-22]. However, some of the causes and Africa are: causes of corruption in Nigeria, colonial legacy, prolonged military rule, poverty, pressures from extended family, commitments and the nature of societal values and expectations, social security among others. The effects, consequences or repercussions of corruption will now be examined. Some of these are: destabilization, increase in poverty, inefficiency and lack of productivity, inflation and threat to economy, threat to development, and battered image. From the

foregoing analysis, it is obvious that corruption causes underdevelopment and that corruption is check-mating growth and development of Africa.

Political Factors

Political crises, election malpractices with their attendant consequences as witnessed in Nigeria during the first, second and third Republics cause underdevelopment. For instance, the Nigerian Civil War which broke out on July 6, 1967 and lasted for thirty months claimed several lives and destroyed valuable property. Also, political instability is manifesting itself in Africa as a chronic symptom of the underdevelopment of political life within the imperialist context. Military coups have followed one after the other, usually meaning nothing to the mass of the people, and sometimes representing a reactionary reversal of the efforts at national liberation. For instance, the post-election violence in Bauchi State in April, 2011 in which many Youth Corps members who were of course, leaders of tomorrow were brutally murdered. The question is: will this not deter foreigners from investing in Nigeria vis-à-vis her development?

Effects of Underdevelopment

One of these effects is low level of income. Others are: low labour productivity, high rate of illiteracy, abject poverty, poor standard of living of the masses, low level of infrastructural facilities, high rate of diseases, high mortality rate, high rate of unemployment, and general insecurity of lives and property. The crises in Jos, Borno and Bauchi, Jigawa, Kano and Gombe states and other states have resulted in the loss of precious lives and valuable property.

Proposed Solutions to the Problem of Underdevelopment in Africa

To remedy a problem, it should first be exposed. Then, one must carefully diagnose its causes, prescribe a solution, and monitor the efficacy of the prescription. To this end therefore, we shall now propose some solutions, which if strictly adhered to, will solve, to a large extent, Africa's problem of underdevelopment.

They consist in full development and full employment of every African – man or woman, child or adolescent. Whatever ideology African leaders choose to adopt, we must note from the outset that they make full development and full employment of every African their first and topmost priority and the cornerstone of all their development plans. Full development and full employment of man are inseparably complementary. To pursue one without the other is not only not to achieve the objective of rapid economic development, but also, to do wanton social injustice and inequity to every African who is discriminated against in the process. Also, African countries need to dismantle all the economic structures erected by the imperialists during the colonial period and build new ones which will genuinely promote their

development. It is imperative for the new States or underdeveloped countries to overthrow neo-colonialism and other forms of foreign domination.

What do all these mean in concrete terms? Since only a very small minority of African families can cater for the full development of their members and use their positions in society to secure full employment for those members, it follows that the state must accept full responsibility for the provision of education at all levels and health facilities free of charge, employment for every African without discrimination. Health facilities we must note, does not consist in the provision of hospitals alone. They embrace the whole compass of preventive medical facilities, good food, good water, decent housing and a clean and wholesome environment. African countries should eliminate all sources of wastage spending and block all loopholes which aliens exploit to cart away their resources. The new state should endeavour to develop an internal-oriented economy. Again, underdeveloped countries should dismantle all the economic structures erected by the imperialists during the colonial period and build new ones which will genuinely promote their development. It is vital for the new states or underdeveloped countries to overthrow neo-colonialism and other forms of foreign domination.

Above all, it is interesting and instructive to note that if African leaders apply the proposed solutions or better still subscribe tenaciously to these proposed solutions, it is my firm belief that Africa will develop and join the comity of Nations.

Conclusion

From the foregoing analysis, we have explained in detailed an overview of the problem of underdevelopment in Africa. In the course of this paper, it is obvious that underdevelopment is a paradox in Africa, simply because, Africa is abundantly endowed with human and natural resources, yet, she is poor. Africa is now home to the world's largest number of developed countries. The continent further boasts of the largest refugee population in the world. It is a theatre of endless conflicts. Civil strives and gross human rights abuses, high unemployment, poverty, malnutrition and desertification appears to be the only legacy the continent is capable of passing from one generation to the other.

Again, Mazrui lends credence to this when he opines that "Africa as a whole, borrowed the wrong things from the West. We borrowed the acquisitive appetite of capitalism, but not the creative risk taking. We are at home with Western gadgets, but are bewildered by workshops. We wear the wristwatch, but refuse to watch it for the culture of punctuality. We have learnt to parade in display, but not to drill in discipline. The West's consumption pattern has arrived, but not necessarily the West's technique of production" [Mazrui Ali, p. 22]. We have equally discussed the meaning, nature, features, the root causes and effects of underdevelopment in Africa. Efforts are also made to proffer some solutions which I believe, if strictly followed

or pursued, will go a long way in solving the problem so that Africa will join the league of advanced Nations. I believe my analysis will provoke some thoughts on how we can solve the problem such that the generality of Africans will not be suffering in the midst of plenty.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Achebe, Chinua (1983). *The Trouble with Nigeria*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publication.
2. Achebe, Chinua (1988). *Anthills of the Savannah*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books.
3. Achebe, Chinua (2012). *There Was A Country: A Personal History of Biafra*. U.S.A.: The Penguin Press.
4. Adebayo, Augustus (1986). *Power in Politics*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited.
5. Awolowo, Obafemi (1972). *An Analysis of the Basic Causes and Remedies of Economic Backwardness*. Ibadan: University of Ibadan.
6. Awolowo, Obafemi (1968). *The Path to Economic Freedom in Developing Countries*. Lagos: An Annual Lecture Delivered at University of Lagos.
7. Awolowo, Obafemi (1977). *The Need for Ideological Reappraisal*. London: Macmillan Education Ltd.
8. Azenabor, Godwin (2007). *Corruption in Nigeria: Perspectives and Strategies for Effective Control*. Lagos: Faculty of Arts, University of Lagos, Monograph Series.
9. Babawale, Tunde (2004). *Culture, Politics and Sustainable Development: Lessons for Nigeria*. Lagos: CBAAC.
10. George, Oladapo (2012). *Diabetic Economy: A Paradox and a Dilemma*. An Inaugural Lecture, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye.
11. Handelman, Howard (2005). *The Challenge of Third World Development*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
12. Lewis, W.A. (1963). *The Theory of Economic Growth*. London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd.
13. Mazrui, Ali (1980). *Cultural Forces in the World Politics*. Portsmouth: Heinemann Educational Books Inc.
14. Mazrui, Ali (1980). *The Africans*. London: BBC Publications.
15. Momoh, C. S. (1991). *Philosophy of A New Past and An Old Future*. Auch: African Philosophy Projects Publications.
16. Mugabe, R. (1991). *Africa in the New World Under Europe 1992 and Beyond*. Daily Times, January 10.
17. Ndubuisi, F.N. (2001). *Contextual Issues in Philosophy of Science*. Lagos: Bendona & Associates.
18. Nkrumah, Kwame (1970). *Consciencism: Philosophy and Ideology for Decolonization*. London: Monthly Review Press.
19. Nwoko, Matthew (1992). *Philosophy of Technology and Nigeria*. Owerri: Claretian Institute of Philosophy.

20. Ogundowole, Kolawole (1988). *Self-Reliancism: Philosophy of A New Order*. Ikeja: John West Publications Ltd.
21. Ogungbemi, Segun (2007). *Philosophy and Development*. Ibadan: Hope Publications.
22. Ogunmodede, Francis Ishola (1985). *Chief Obafemi Awolowo's Socio-Political Philosophy: A Critical Interpretation*. Ibadan: Intec Printers Limited.
23. Oladipo, Olusegun, & Olorunyomi, Sola (eds.) (1999). *Viewpoint: A Critical Review of Culture and Society*. Ibadan: Hope Publications.
24. Opafofa, O. Sulaimon (1997). *The Idea of Development: A Philosophical Analysis*. Lagos: Samtech Communications.
25. Rodney, Walter (1972). *Scholarship on African Development-An Overview*. The Center for Afro-American and African Studies, Colloquium on Africa, March 13.
26. Russell, Bertrand (1985). *Principles of Social Reconstruction*. London: Routledge.
27. Unah, Jim (1995). *Essays in Philosophy*. Lagos: Panaf Press.
28. Timamy, Khalil (2007). *The Political Economy of Technological Underdevelopment in Africa*. Lagos: Centre for Black and African Arts Civilization (CBAAC).
29. Unah, Jim (1995). *Essays in Philosophy*. Lagos: Panaf Press.
30. Unah, Jim (1996). *Heidegger's Existentialism: An Essay on Applied Ontology*. Lagos: Panaf Press.

